

Matching Uni-Directional Auditory Gestures to Visual Trajectories of Varying Curvature

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ABSTRACT

A perceptual experiment tested the ability of listeners to match uni-directional auditory gestures along either pitch, loudness or tempo with corresponding visual trajectories. Within each parameter, the auditory gestures varied across different acoustic scales or functions and could be matched dynamically to trajectories of varying curvature (e.g., linear, exponential, logarithmic). The gestures investigated spanned different frequency and sound-level ranges as well as durations. Results from the analysis of global trends suggest that listeners can reliably distinguish between the studied auditory gestures and moreover relate them to analogous visual trajectories. The identified audiovisual associations may find utility in different scenarios of sound design or production.

1. INTRODUCTION

In many perceptual scenarios, we may encounter continuous glides in frequency or sound level or sequences containing accelerating or decelerating sound events. These acoustic cues can evoke the perception of auditory gestures along either pitch, loudness, or tempo, respectively, which may in turn convey analogies to motion trajectories or visual representations. This relates to a growing body of research on crossmodal correspondences [1], e.g., that between pitch and spatial elevation, and studies on sonic trajectories [2, 3] or shapes [4]. Apart from myriad potential uses in applications for sonification or auditory displays, sound-based *gestures* assume a central role in *spectromorphology* [5], one of the major theories in electroacoustic music. Similarly, a catalog of typical gestures has also been proposed under the term *unités sémiotiques temporelles* and perceptually validated [6]. In the past decade, investigations on sound gestures, e.g., [7–9], identified suitable auditory parameters and their mapping onto spatial or motion-related dimensions, also in terms of magnitude and orientation, whereas none of these studies looked more closely into perceptual differences between implied gestural trajectories or shapes.

Aiming to fill that gap, the current study investigated the association between basic, uni-directional auditory gestures

and analogous visual trajectories. More specifically, pitch, loudness or tempo gestures were studied that either increased or decreased along the relevant acoustic parameter over time. The functional dependency across time was of primary interest, in terms of what visual trajectory was perceptually matched for a given acoustic scale or function. The interest in such audiovisual associations is motivated by their widespread use in sound-based applications. For instance, in many cases when a frequency-related dimension is visualised across time, the display maps low to high frequencies from bottom to top, as in spectrograms or Western musical notation. If such a visualisation depicted a straight line increasing in frequency over time, what shape would the auditory pitch gesture correspond to? For one, this of course depends on the frequency scale used in the visualisation, but it also depends on the scale or function underlying the increase in frequency over time, e.g., a psychoacoustic scale such as equivalent rectangular bandwidth (ERB) rate [10]. Likewise, loudness gestures may result from different ways to scale the signal amplitude. In digital audio workstation (DAW) software, for instance, linear or curved shapes are commonly applied as fade-in/out control functions. Do these visual shapes also extend to the shape or gesture of the resulting change in loudness if they for most parts are applied to the amplitude and not the sound-level representation? Similar scenarios, are conceivable for the use of visual trajectories to describe tempo changes.

The current study follows an exploratory approach, by considering a range of functions, most of which have been studied before or find common application in sound production or manipulation scenarios. Although knowledge of psychoacoustic scalings allowed certain hypotheses to be derived, for instance, on a function that could be perceived as most linear, i.e., corresponding to a straight line, the main aim was to also consider options that allow for a variety of gestural shapes and curvatures, as all them could be of value in sound-design applications.

2. METHOD

A perceptual listening experiment was conducted to investigate what visual trajectories would be matched to uni-directional gestures along pitch, loudness, and tempo, involving four acoustic functions per parameter and spanning multiple ranges across frequency, sound level, and tempo or duration.

2.1 Participants

Twenty participants (15 male, 5 female) with a median age of 21 years (range: 18–51) completed the experiment. They were recruited from the wider community of De Montfort University. Participation in the experiment involved informed consent, and the procedure had received prior approval by the Research Ethics Committee of De Montfort University. Participants were offered remuneration for their involvement.

2.2 Stimuli

All auditory gestures studied shared the following signal properties, rendered as PCM audio data at 44.1 kHz sample rate and 24-bit dynamic resolution. All gestures involved band-pass filtered pink noise using a second-order Butterworth design and a constant relative bandwidth, $Q = 11.5$. Tab. 1 displays the common signal properties for the filter’s center frequency, the presented sound pressure level (SPL) and two possible gesture durations in bold, which define those signal properties that remained unaffected by a particular auditory parameter under study. For instance, pitch and tempo gestures were always presented at 64 dB SPL, whereas loudness and tempo gestures always concerned 1 kHz filter centre frequency. Likewise, pitch and loudness gestures were studied for two durations that matched the *slower* and *faster* tempo gestures under study.

2.2.1 Pitch gestures

Pitch gestures comprised a continuous glide in frequency that spanned two octaves, in which frequency varied between individual audio samples along normalised time, $t = [0, 1]$. As shown in Tab. 1, these two-octave gestures occurred below and above the 1 kHz anchor, corresponding to *lower* and *higher* pitch ranges, respectively. In addition, pitch gestures also occurred in both *ascending* and *descending* orientations and for a *shorter* and *longer* duration, all of which functioned as independent variables (IVs).

Four acoustic functions studied how the filter’s centre frequency, representing perceived *pitch*, varied between the specified low and high frequencies. As shown in Fig. 1, the four functions concerned either a linear increase over time in frequency in Hz (A) or a linear increase in ERB number (B). The remaining two functions concerned an exponential dependency approximately twice the curvature of ERB rate (C) and a function that formed a logarithmic trajectory (D) of inverse curvature to the third.

2.2.2 Loudness gestures

Loudness gestures involved continuous ramped amplitude envelopes that spanned an equivalent sound-level difference of 18 dB across normalised time. As illustrated in Tab. 1, these ramps operated at *softer* and *louder* levels around the 64 dB SPL anchor. Similar to pitch, loudness gestures occurred for both *increasing* and *decreasing* orientations and for the same two durations, again serving as IVs.

Fig. 2 depicts the four functions that determined the change in relative amplitude (left panel) or equivalent change in

Figure 1. Four time functions A, B, C, and D for frequency scaling studied for pitch gestures. The displayed functions correspond to the *higher* frequency range and *ascending* orientation.

sound level in dB over time. The functions concerned linear trajectories along amplitude (A) and sound level in dB (B), respectively. Function C complemented the remaining functions with an inverse, logarithmic curvature. Function D corresponded to a raised-cosine amplitude envelope or *S curve*. All four functions are common options for audio fades in DAWs, e.g., *Pro Tools*, *Reaper*.

2.2.3 Tempo gestures

Tempo gestures concerned a series of 16 noise bursts whose tempo between beginning and end changed by a factor two, relative to the anchor tempo of 360 ‘bursts’ per minute (BPM). Each burst concerned an identical 90-ms noise segment with a Gaussian amplitude envelope. Tempo gestures could either *accelerate* or *decelerate* and occurred at two levels, *slower* and *faster*. The median duration of tempo gestures (across the functions below) per tempo level also served as the durations for pitch and loudness gestures.

The functions were gathered from previous studies on tempo *ritardandi* or decelerations. Accelerating gestures used the same functions in the inverse sense. The first three functions employed the $1/q$ power expression proposed by Friberg & Sundberg [11]. As illustrated in Fig. 3, Function A, with $q = 1$, represents a linear decrease along normalised score position, whereas Function B, $q = 2.5$, reflects the optimum range found by Friberg & Sundberg to be perceived as the most ‘musical’. Function C, $q = -1/2.5$, mirrored the former with an inverse curvature. The fourth function employed the quadratic inter onset interval (IOI) by Repp [12].

2.3 Experimental Procedure

Participants were asked to match auditory gestures to an analogous visual line segment, with the x-axis reflecting time and the y-axis the parameter range under consideration, namely, *low to high* for pitch, *soft to loud* for loudness, and *slow to fast* for tempo. Using a continuous slider

	Bottom	Parameter ranges			Top
			Anchor		
Pitch gesture		<i>lower</i>		<i>higher</i>	
Frequency (Hz)	250	← →	1,000	← →	4,000
Loudness gesture		<i>softer</i>		<i>louder</i>	
SPL (dB)	46	← →	64	← →	82
Tempo gesture		<i>slower</i>		<i>faster</i>	
BPM	180	← →	360	← →	720
Median duration (s)		3.51		1.80	

Table 1. Parameter ranges across frequency, sound pressure level (SPL), and bursts per minute (BPM) used in the pitch, loudness, and tempo gestures, respectively. Gestures along each parameter were investigated at two levels, e.g., a *lower* and a *higher* pitch range, spanning bottom-to-anchor and anchor-to-top ranges, respectively. Parameter values in *bold* also represent the base settings for gestures along the remaining parameters.

Figure 2. Functions investigated for loudness gestures, in *decreasing* orientation. The left panel visualises the 18-dB decrease in normalised amplitude, whereas the right panel displays the same functions in relative sound level.

Figure 3. Functions investigated for tempo gestures, in *decelerating* orientation from normalised full to half tempo.

next to the visual trajectory, as shown in Fig. 4, participants were asked to match their perception of auditory gestures to analogous visual trajectories, spanning a continuum from exponential to logarithmic curvature, corresponding to the numeric values $[-0.7,+0.7]$, with 0.0 yielding a straight line.¹ Slider movements above the center (0.0) yielded varying degrees of upward, logarithmic curvature, whereas slider movements below the center yielded downward, exponential curvatures.

In a single trial, participants compared and rated a triplet of the acoustic functions A–D, i.e., the four contexts ABC, ABD, ACD, or BCD. Trials for pitch and loudness gestures each comprised 4 contexts \times 2 orientations \times 2 durations \times 2 levels. Tempo gestures consisted of all but the last IV, as its purpose was already covered by the two durations. In total, the experiment comprised 80 trials, in which trials for pitch, loudness, and tempo gestures were tested in separate blocks, with their order counter-balanced across participants.

¹ Max 8’s *function* object was used for the GUI and data acquisition. The underlying functional dependency between its value range $[-0.7,0.7]$ and the curvature of line segments was thereupon numerically approximated in MATLAB.

Figure 4. Graphical user interface (GUI) for experimental trials for the comparison of three pitch gestures (e.g., ACD). Participants could listen to each gesture in isolation and had to match the curvature of the respective auditory gesture by using the red slider. Left, center, and right panels illustrate exponential, linear, and logarithmic curvatures, respectively.

3. RESULTS

Although the data acquisition has been completed, more detailed data analysis is still ongoing and only overall findings on the clearest global trends in the data will be presented here. The focus lies on illustrating how the four acoustic functions A–D tested for pitch, loudness, and tempo gestures map onto the analogous visual trajectories participants matched their perception. Overall, the patterns shown were obtained regardless of gesture duration, gesture orientation, and also frequency or sound-level range, where applicable.

Furthermore, the reported data for individual functions concern averaged values across the three contexts a single function occurred in, e.g., for function A in contexts ABC, ABD, and ACD. Although contextual variation of ratings did affect the magnitude of ratings, the rank order of ratings among functions did not vary much. Based on this, it is reasonable to assume the average to be representative of each function given the global context A–D.

3.1 Pitch gestures

Pitch gestures yielded the clearest differences between the acoustic functions A–D, as shown in Fig. 5. The analogous visual trajectory for ERB rate, based on its median ratings, matched the straight linear line closest, whereas linear frequency scaling in Hz led to a slightly logarithmic curvature. The suggested ‘linearity’ of ERB rate, which corresponds to an exponential function across linear frequency scaling, therefore agrees with previous psychoacoustic research on the logarithmic frequency scaling of the human auditory system [10]. Moreover, ERB rate also likens the prevalent scaling for musical intervals, e.g., a pitch continuum P scaled along index n using $P(n) = f_{min} * (f_{max}/f_{min})^n$, for any ratio between an upper and lower frequency (f_{max} and f_{min}). In the experiment, only the frequency function exhibiting twice the curvature of the above dependency (function B) was matched to a clearly exponential line segment. Likewise, also the logarithmic scaling of frequency was associated to the curvature of a logarithm function.

The perceived differences among A–D were furthermore confirmed in a repeated-measures, four-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), [$F(1.3, 24.5) = 95, \varepsilon = .043, p < .001, \eta_G^2 = .524$]. Notably, the perceptual distinction

was robust against all but one of the remaining IVs. Frequency range only introduced little variation to gestural shape, however, [$\eta_G^2 = .075$].

3.2 Loudness gestures

Loudness gestures also yielded clear differences among the acoustic functions, as shown in Fig. 6. Gestures varying along linear amplitude were matched with a straight linear trajectory, whereas the raised-cosine function (S curve) was perceived as slightly exponential. Somewhat surprisingly, a linear scaling along sound level in dB was matched to a markedly exponential trajectory. Whereas this finding could be specific to the context of functions A–D studied, it is notable that the same four functions are common options for fade-ins and fade-outs in DAW software. Furthermore, the matched visual trajectories mirror the shapes depicted in Fig. 2’s left panel more than the right panel. In other words, waveform displays using relative amplitude as opposed to sound level in dB as the y-axis scale may in fact estimate the perceived loudness gesture better.

Again, ANOVA confirmed the perceptual differences among A–D as a clear main effect, ($F(1.1, 21.7) = 61, \varepsilon = 0, p < .001, \eta_G^2 = .367$). Unlike for pitch, however, a number of other IVs contributed to main or interaction effects, namely sound-level range, duration, and orientation, all with markedly smaller effect size [$\eta_G^2 \leq .089$].

3.3 Tempo gestures

Tempo gestures exhibited the weakest and most ambiguous results. The curvature deviating most from a straight linear segment was obtained for function C, corresponding to $q = -1/2.5$. This function was considered as a logarithmic dependency to complement the remaining functions, which had been derived from perceptual research on *ritardandi*. Among the three latter, however, differences were small. Still, the function for $q = 2.5$ approximated a straight line most closely. This reflects previous findings on a preference of $q = 2$ or $q = 3$ power functions over the $q = 1$ option [11] or the squared IOI dependency [12].

The weak and ambiguous results were also reflected in a pronounced variation across triplet contexts, which yielded violations of order, e.g., $B > D > A$ vs. $D > B > C$. As this contextual variation did not warrant that averages across contexts would represent reliable descriptions of the

Figure 5. Boxplot (left) for the pitch-gesture ratings (averaged across triplet contexts) for the frequency functions A–D, across all participants and collapsed across all remaining IVs ($N = 160$). Visual analogues of the line segments (right) based on the boxplot medians that reflect what participants would have seen. Notches represent 95% confidence intervals for the medians.

Figure 6. Boxplot (left) for the loudness-gesture ratings (averaged across triplet contexts) for the frequency functions A–D, across all participants and collapsed across all remaining IVs ($N = 160$). Visual analogues of the line segments (right) based on the boxplot medians that reflect what participants would have seen. Notches represent 95% confidence intervals for the medians.

Figure 7. Boxplot (left) for the tempo-gesture ratings (averaged across triplet contexts) for the frequency functions A–D, across all participants and collapsed across all remaining IVs ($N = 80$). Visual analogues of the line segments (right) based on the boxplot medians that reflect what participants would have seen. Notches represent 95% confidence intervals for the medians.

gestural shapes among A–D, no further analysis was conducted.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of global trends suggests that listeners can reliably perceive differences between uni-directional auditory gestures, at least for pitch and loudness, and associate them to analogous visual trajectories, the shape of which implies the perceived shape of the auditory gesture. The conducted multifactorial ANOVA confirmed the global trends for pitch and loudness gestures, while also identifying effects across the IVs, which did not compromise the relative perceptual distinction of gestural shapes, however. Pitch and loudness gestures were robust against contextual variation, whereas the weak perceptual distinction of tempo gestures led to contextual ambiguity and rendered the observed trends unreliable.

For pitch and loudness at least, visual trajectories of varying curvature can be used to describe auditory gestures, and provided the use of perceptually informed acoustic scales, they could also be used as effective visual aids to control auditory gestures.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] C. Spence, “Crossmodal correspondences: a tutorial review.” *Attention, perception & psychophysics*, vol. 73, no. 4, pp. 971–995, 2011.
- [2] A. Merer, M. Aramaki, S. Ystad, and R. Kronland-Martinnet, “Perceptual characterization of motion evoked by sounds for synthesis control purposes,” *ACM Transactions on Applied Perception*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 1–24, 2013.
- [3] E. Thoret, M. Aramaki, R. Kronland-Martinnet, J.-L. Velay, and S. Ystad, “From sound to shape: Auditory perception of drawing movements.” *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 983–994, 2014.
- [4] S.-A. Lembke, “Hearing triangles: Perceptual clarity, opacity, and symmetry of spectrotemporal sound shapes,” *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 144, no. 2, pp. 608–619, 2018.
- [5] D. Smalley, “Spectromorphology: explaining sound-shapes,” *Organised Sound*, vol. 2, no. 2, p. S1355771897009059, 1997.
- [6] A. Frey, A. Daquet, S. Poitrenaud, C. Tijus, M. Fremiot, M. Formosa, L. Prod’Homme, J. Mandelbrojt, M. Timsit-Berthier, P. Bootz, X. Hautbois, and M. Besson, “Pertinence cognitive des unités sémiotiques temporelles,” *Musicae Scientiae*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 415–440, 2009.
- [7] K. Nymoen, J. Torresen, R. I. Godøy, and A. R. Jensenius, “A Statistical Approach to Analyzing Sound Tracings,” in *Speech, Sound and Music Processing: Embracing Research in India*, ser. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, S. Ystad, M. Aramaki, R. Kronland-Martinnet, K. Jensen, and D. Mohanty, Eds. Berlin/Heidelberg: Springer, 2012, vol. 7172, pp. 120–145.
- [8] M. B. Küssner, D. Tidhar, H. M. Prior, and D. Leech-Wilkinson, “Musicians are more consistent: Gestural cross-modal mappings of pitch, loudness and tempo in real-time,” *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 5, no. July, pp. 1–15, jul 2014.
- [9] G. Lemaitre, H. Scurto, J. Françoise, F. Bevilacqua, O. Houix, and P. Susini, “Rising tones and rustling noises: Metaphors in gestural depictions of sounds,” *PLOS ONE*, vol. 12, no. 7, p. e0181786, jul 2017.
- [10] B. C. J. Moore and B. R. Glasberg, “Suggested formulae for calculating auditory filter bandwidths and excitation patterns,” *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 74, no. 3, pp. 750–753, 1983.
- [11] A. Friberg and J. Sundberg, “Does music performance allude to locomotion? A model of final ritardandi derived from measurements of stopping runners,” *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 105, no. 3, pp. 1469–1484, 1999.
- [12] B. H. Repp, “Diversity and commonality in music performance: An analysis of timing microstructure in Schumann’s “Träumerei”,” *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 92, no. 5, pp. 2546–2568, 1992.